

Two Poems in English by SK

“A Gentle’s Song” – In Memoriam of AJH

“Death is not sensed as a defeat but as a summation, an arrival, a conclusion.”
– Abraham Joshua Heschel)

“rivers.net”

Amazon flows calmly, oblivious to all-too-anthropoidal noises—money, power, politics, sports, idolatries—
less-than-idyllic entertainments for hominids hibernating in mass transits, mass media, mass absurdities.

“A Gentle’s Song” – In Memoriam of AJH

“Death is not sensed as a defeat but as a summation, an arrival, a conclusion.”
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Death is NOT something
That awaits me at the end of my words
As the last word to my gasping breath, my tiny logos.
Death bursts open its bubble memory,
Blaming on me and you, our ailing nature, unborn child.
With esoteric astrophysical grammar
Of black holes and white dwarfs,
As irrelevant vocabulary, death, it is “Nein.”

“O death, where is thy sting?
O grave, where is thy victory?” 1 Corinthians 15:55)

Despite unprepared, demonized and bleak,
As irrational words, numbers, and such,
Death, quietly, becomes the sum of positive numbers,
Out of the total of imaginary and negative numbers.

Death, no longer a blasphemy to the enlightened,
Arrives at predestined space-time of destiny.
Pulled by the imagined gentle gravity,
It glides along the curvature of space-time
To the massively parallel hopes of connectivity.

A welcoming phrase is felt, heard and lived
As my logos, I-Thou, resumes flowing
And mixing in flux of old and new, wise and fool.
Steeped in Arabian song of many dialects,
Out of ancient blue, the echoes of a pronouncement
To the ears which can hear,
Arrives the breath of Logos in epiphany and rebirth.

That which unites me and you in the eternal Thou,
Abides in the Logos of "Thus saith the Lord."
Quickened by the breath of Logos in the evening,
In the shifting sands and mirages of the desert,
In my land and your land, Arabia, we die and begin anew.

In the ever-present cosmos next to old Arabia,
Where our ancestors could only dream about,
I open the script of summation-arrival-conclusion
To avail myself to yourselves for the unfinished dialogue,
The Logos which I heard and read in the desert
With many tears of fear, trembling and, finally, Joy.

(In that day there will be a highway from Egypt to Assyria. The Assyrians will go to Egypt and the Egyptians to Assyria. The Egyptians and Assyrians will worship together. In that day Israel will be the third, along with Egypt and Assyria, a blessing on the earth. The Lord Almighty will bless them, saying, "Blessed be Egypt my people, Assyria my handiwork, and Israel my inheritance." Isaiah 19:23-25)

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oblivious
to all-too-anthropoidal noises—
money, power, politics,
sports, idolatries—
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for hominids hibernating
in mass transits, mass media,
mass absurdities.

A monkey business.

Yet flow, rivers,
flow your tears
into bloody, dry eyes
of mothers
for the motherless children lost
in alleys and valleys,
in tents and tenements,
in gutters and ghettos,
in water and fire.

Mankind delivered
at your/my doorstep.

Unlimited free delivery—
he said, she said,
some said 'who?'

Dusts and crumbs
swept into coffins,
shipped down shifting tributaries.

33 satellites
search for holes in the ground—
pre-ordered coffins
keep landing ashore
for the next of kin
to motherless children.

Mankind delivered
at your/my doorstep.

Unlimited tracking info—
genetically coded
in ISO gibberish.

They flow
at the speed of electrons
in rivers of alternating current,
seen only
in black and white stripes.

No telling how to decipher,
how to whisper.

Mind you,
no two zebras look alike.

All rivers merge
in weebegone disarray,
drenched hot
in the gushing of tears:

despair to silence,
silence to *muchas nada*,
nada
to ubiquity.

360 is the degree of freedom
inherited
by the so-called wise.

No trajectory,

no arc—
only intuition and gut.

Gravity, with its 360 tragedies,
spreads wings
where 4D simulations
are obsolete,
where potholes
and black holes
guide us
mid-polar reversal.

Dig, rivers, dig
your habitual channels
calmly,
at the speed of silence—

to a point
yet to be poked,
to a plane
yet to be wrinkled,
to a warehouse
built long ago
by Adam Smith.

Here,
and in most GMT zones,
we mourn
the Black Death
of centuries past,
the black deaths
from wrong skin
at the wrong place,
wrong time.

New coffins
cold-molded en masse
in China—
one size fits all,
duty-free—
in transit
for mankind
delivered
at your/my doorstep.

Almost midnight,
as texted:
books and music
will be delivered,
until the sun burns out

its fire and smoke,
until funds vomit
round the loop—
NYC—Shanghai—London—Zurich—NYC.

For mothers
weak in gut and instinct,
nickels jingle:
'In God We Trust,'
echoed in fogs
of deaths
and muted cries—
fountains,
rivers,
oceans—
flickering light years
eternizing
tears and cries
of quivering babes.

All is calm
and all is bright
at your doorstep,

transaction approved
long before scan
of zebra stripes
tattooed
on my forehead
by ICE.

From customer service:

Refund?
Two bribes required—
inside
and outside the US.

No bribe?
Request rejected:
lack of info
and moral honesty.

No refund?
Proof of birth
waived
if death certificate
is filed
before death.

Filed before death.
Delivered
at your / my doorstep.

10/2018 sk 羽河, revised 2/2023 and 11/24/2025
(muchas nada: 'many nothing', Hemingway, 1933)
("...best decisions: intuition and gut..." — Jeff Bezos, 9/2018)